

National Conference on Biodiversity and Plant Genetic Resource Conservation for Future

15th - 16th March, 2019

**COMPENDIUM
OF
ABSTRACTS**

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National Conference on
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Evaluation of Tropical Forage Legume -Hedge lucerne (*Desmanthusvirgatus*(L.) Willd) genotypes for different biometric, quality and physiological traits.

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ABSTRACT

The present study entitled “Evaluation of Hedge lucerne (*Desmanthusvirgatus*(L.) Willd) genotypes for different biometric, quality and physiological traits” was carried out in the Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, College of Agriculture, Vellayani during 2016-2018 with an objective to evaluate the leguminous fodder crop Hedge lucerne (*Desmanthusvirgatus*(L.) Willd) in terms of biometric, quality and physiological traits. The characters were evaluated during each four harvest with eight genotypes. The genotype 'Thumburmuzhi local' showed highest plant height, number of branches per plant, length of branches, dry matter production, crop growth rate, net assimilation rate, green fodder yield, dry fodder yield, crude

protein and crude fibre content in four harvest of crop. The study concluded that genotype 'Thumburmuzhi local' could be utilized for various crop improvement programs, it has high potential to exploit through different breeding aspects.

